

Current status of ticks (Acari: Argasidae, Ixodidae) in India

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Abstract

Ticks are large chelicerate, ectoparasitic vectors belonging to arthropods causing several zoonotic tick-borne diseases leading to morbidity or even mortality in both humans and animals worldwide. From India, 125 species are recorded which is more than one-eighth of the 982 tick species, belonging to 24 genera (10 from India) and 4 families namely Ixodidae, Argasidae, Nuttalliellidae and Deinocerotonidae known from the world. Out of the 125 Indian tick species, 105 species belong to the family Ixodidae, and 20 species to the family Argasidae. Due to its diversity and medico-veterinary significance, there is a need for surveillance of ticks and tick-borne diseases in India. The main objective of this publication is to provide an updated list of tick species occurring in India. Here, a valid and updated species belonging to ticks found in the Indian sub-continent is prepared with its distribution pattern in India.

Keywords: *Distribution, Host, India, Ticks, Updated checklist, valid species.*

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Introduction

India provides a sanctuary for the vertical distribution of abundant fauna and has a conducive wide range of ecological and climatic conditions. There are a large number of species that occur in a variety of habitats. There are still areas that have not been adequately explored. So far there has been no in-depth enumeration of the Ixodida group despite important vectors from the medical and veterinary standpoints. At one or more developmental stages, ticks are blood-feeding ectoparasites and majority of the species infest mammals, birds, reptiles, and amphibians. There are a large number of tick species recognized as vectors of lethal pathogens, viz. Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever virus (CCHFV), Kyasanur forest disease virus (KFDV), *Babesia* spp., *Theileria* spp., *Rickettsia conorii*, *Anaplasma marginale*, etc. responsible for considerable losses to the livestock industry (Grisi *et al.*, 2014). Ticks can transmit a myriad of pathogens causing significant morbidity and mortality in companion animals and humans (Dantas-Torres

et al., 2012, Dantas-Torres and Otranto, 2016). There is a need to assess the renewed threat posed by the tick vectors and to prioritize the tick control research program.

In recent years, there is an increasing public health concern over tick-borne diseases in many parts of India. Hence to update the Ticks fauna in India, a systematic list of Ixodida: Argasidae and Ixodidae distribution so far recorded and reported from the Indian subcontinent is reviewed. Worldwide more than 982 species of Ticks are recorded and 125 species are reported from different parts of India (Nijhof *et al.*, 2019; Dantas-Torres *et al.*, 2019; Guglielmone *et al.*, 2015, 2023). This publication is the updated comprehensive inventory of the ticks of India using published records and from our surveillance data conducted in Tamil Nadu and Kerala (Tiwari and Hiriyani, 1988, 1989; Krishnamoorthi *et al.*, 2020; Philip Samuel *et al.*, 2020a, b, 2021). A compiled updated checklist of the Indian ticks includes a total of 125 tick species belonging to two

families Ixodidae and Argasidae and the comprehensive results are presented in this publication (Table 1).

Ticks constitute the worst vectors of many diseases of human and veterinary importance caused by pathogens like viruses, rickettsial bacteria, spirochaetes, and protozoans (Arthur, 1962). A literature survey showed that the first checklist about the Indian ticks was undertaken by Sharif in 1928 who recorded 45 species from the Indian museum collections. A second checklist was prepared by Sen (1938) who recorded 50 species of ticks from India. Jagannath *et al.* (1973) recorded the Ixodid ticks of domestic stock in Tamil Nadu and presented a checklist of Indian ticks consisting of 99 species belonging to 11 genera. A checklist of 160 Indian ticks included many undetermined tick species and synonyms (Miranpuri and Naithani, 1978). Geevarghese, Fernandes and Kulkarni (1997) prepared a checklist including all the valid tick species collected from different hosts in different regions of the country which included 106 tick species belonging to two families Ixodidae and Argasidae.

Gap areas

Like other animal groups, there are few studies undertaken on ticks and the systematic list of Ixodida is prepared to understand the species diversity of this group which included our studies in Tamil Nadu and Kerala (Tiwari and Hiriyan, 1988, 1989; Krishnamoorthi *et al.*, 2020; Philip Samuel *et al.*, 2020a, b, 2021). There is a rich diversity of ticks feeding on mammals, reptiles, amphibians, and bird hosts available in India and there is every possibility of many new species in India yet to be discovered. There has still not been a survey exclusively for this group in the entire country for want of experts. It is required to undertake in-depth studies on ticks and their disease-causing agents on animal and human hosts with their possible role as vectors in the transmission of the different pathogens. Further research in this field is required in the less surveyed areas like Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, and Rajasthan will yield additional new tick species which will bring forth deeper insights into the tick systematic in India.

Discussion

Ticks are the most abundantly available creatures found mainly in the tropical and subtropical regions which are responsible for considerable possession of the livestock industry. An attempt was made to publish an updated checklist based on the different publications available which will streamline the future research activities on the tick species recorded in India. In 1991 and 1993, there were approximately 820 species of ticks recorded all over the world with 19 genera belonging to 3 families (Sonenshine, 1991, 1993). At present more than 982 species of ticks are recorded worldwide of which 125 species are reported from different parts of India (Nijhof *et al.*, 2019; Dantas-Torres *et al.*, 2019; Guglielmone *et al.*, 2015, 2023). The distribution pattern of tick species of both world and India are mentioned in Table 1 (Guglielmone *et al.*, 2015, 2023).

History of tick taxonomy in India

The first major era in the history of tick taxonomy occurred in the late 1800s and early 1900s. During this period, ticks were sent to a number of European specialists from many independent countries and colonies including India. Knowledge of Indian ticks starts with the description of *Acarus elephantianus* and *Acarus indus* by Linnaeus in 1767 (Geevarghese and Mishra, 2011). Both these species were made invalid by Neuman (1911) in his Monograph "Ixodidae", wherein he described few species under the seven genera from India. In 1910, Warburton published a number of additional species. Later, the classic and comprehensive work entitled "Ticks: A monograph of Ixodidae" Part II & III and IV by Nuttal *et al.*, in 1911, 1915 respectively, gave an account of many Indian species. Sharif (1928) had given a checklist of 45 species from the collection of Indian Museum, Calcutta.

Later, Sen (1938) reported a checklist of 50 species. Discovery of KFD from *H. spinigera* in March 1957 from the Shimoga district of Karnataka stimulated the study on different aspects of Indian ticks. Trapido *et al.* (1964a & 1964b) prepared key for identification of different stages of 14 *Haemaphysalis* species from KFD area. In addition, contributions of

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Table 1: Distribution of tick species across world and India (Guglielmone *et al.*, 2015, 2023; Nijhof *et al.*, 2019)

Family	Genus	World	India
		No of Species	No of valid updated species
Argasidae	<i>Antricola</i>	17	0
	<i>Argas</i>	64	10
	<i>Nothoaspis</i>	2	0
	<i>Ornithodoros</i>	133	9
	<i>Otobius</i>	2	1
Deinocerotonidae	<i>Deinoceroton</i>	1	0
Ixodidae	<i>Africaniella</i>	2	0
	<i>Amblyomma</i>	136	13
	<i>Anomalohimalaya</i>	3	0
	<i>Archaeoceroton</i>	1	0
	<i>Bothrioceroton</i>	7	0
	<i>Compluriscutula</i>	1	0
	<i>Cornupalpatum</i>	1	0
	<i>Cosmiomma</i>	1	0
	<i>Dermacentor</i>	44	3
	<i>Haemaphysalis</i>	176	52
	<i>Hyalomma</i>	27	10
	<i>Ixodes</i>	266	13
	<i>Margaropus</i>	3	0
	<i>Nosomma</i>	2	2
	<i>Rhipiceroton</i>	2	0
	<i>Rhipicephalus</i>	89	12
	<i>Robertsicus</i>	1	0
Nuttalliellidae	<i>Nuttalliella</i>	1	0
4	24	982	125

Harry Hoogstral to the systematics of Indian ticks are worth mentioning (Geevarghese and Mishra, 2011). The checklist published by Miranpuri and Naithani (1972), Jagannath *et al.* (1973) and Geevarghese *et al.* (1997) reported 99 species, 160 species and 106 species, respectively. Subsequently, Ghosh *et al.* (2007)

and (2015) reported the distribution of 110 tick species from India. The present list contains a valid updated 125 tick species reported in India along with their distribution in different states and different host animals are given in Table 2 and Fig. 1.

Tick-borne diseases and vectors

Many species of Ixodida are acting as vectors of many important diseases. Emerging zoonoses are a growing threat to global health and have caused economic damage of hundreds of billions of US dollars in the past 20 years. Zoonotic diseases occur due to various causes including the ecology of pathogens and parasites, environmental modifications due to natural calamities, and other circumstances such as a change in the dynamics of the disease exposure to human beings (Rajagopalan, 2020). Ticks of the families Ixodidae and Argasidae are of medical and veterinary importance and are distributed worldwide. A list of 132 tick species recorded in India is furnished in Table 3. Many species were recorded as vectors of pathogens such as viruses, protozoan, and rickettsia (Padbidri *et al.* 1982; Banerjee and Bhat 1984; Banerjee 1984; Sonenshine 1993; Ghosh and Nagar, 2014). Several tick-borne diseases are caused by different tick vectors with many pathogens, viz. Indian tick typhus (*Rhipicephalus sanguineus*), Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever (*Hyalomma anatolicum*), Kyasanur forest disease (*Haemaphysalis spinigera*), Babesiosis & Bovine anaplasmosis (*Rhipicephalus microplus*), Theileriosis (*Hyalomma anatolicum*), etc. (Ghosh and Nagar, 2014). A total of 6,012 adult and immature ticks belonging to 12 species (11 Ixodid and one Argasid) were collected (Kumar *et al.*, 2014).

In 1994, serologically positive cases of Lyme disease were reported from Coonoor in Nilgiris Hills of Tamil Nadu state (Sharma *et al.*, 1992). During 2007, a major epidemic of Indian tick typhus was reported from villages in Deol district Kangra, Himachal Pradesh where 357 cases were reported (Kumar *et al.*, 2011).

Scope for the modern taxonomy in ticks

Nowadays very few scientists show willingness to undertake research on tick taxonomical aspects. It is very much needed to train up a large number of research scholars in the field situation and also to provide the needful to further carry out the research in this line. Many projects should be undertaken covering different aspects of ticks that will bring forth large number of scientific publications. Barcoding is one such modern method used in

Taxonomy. Lv *et al.* (2014) used mitochondrial cytochrome oxidase I gene (COI) and 16S as a dependable tool to demarcate different species of ticks and also by using 18S to delineate at the genera level. A DNA barcoding system for the Ixodida was already developed by employing new universal primers for 16S, 18S and COI of ticks. Some more research is still required to solve serious problems encountered while using 16S and COI for some of the tick species. This can be taken up in the establishments where adequate services and workforce are present. The qualified manpower will be responsible for the development of this research stationed at different parts of the country which will form a good strength to face the problems encountered by the different tick-borne diseases in India. Some of the tick species were synonymized and few species were deleted from the list of valid historical background of India tick taxonomy (Ghosh *et al.*, 2016) by the recently published compilation of “The hard ticks in the world” by Alberto Guglielmone *et al.* (2013). Krishnamoorthy *et al.* (2021) undertook a molecular survey using the sequence analysis of mitochondrial Cytochrome Oxidase subunit 1 gene on the cattle ticks namely *Ha. bispinosa*, *Ha. japonica*, *Hy. excavatum*, *R. annulatus*, *R. decoloratus*, *R. microplus*, and *R. sanguineus* collected from different agroclimatic zones present in Karnataka and Kerala.

New host

New host records were reported for four tick species *Amblyomma kraneveldi*, *A. pattoni*, *A. gercaisi* and *A. javanense* parasitizing on four species of reptiles. The highest host richness was shown by *H. (K.) bispinosa* and *R. haemaphysaloides* parasitizing six and five different host species, respectively. Reports of *R. (B.) annulatus* on sambar deer, *A. javanense* and *A. kraneveldi* on python as well as *A. pattoni* on Indian rat snake are the new host records from this region (Ajith Kumar *et al.*, 2018).

New places of occurrence

A total of 3,008 domestic animals were examined in areas ranging from an altitude of 300 to 2200 meters above mean sea level (MSL) of which 1335 (44.5%) animals were having tick infestation. A total of 6,012 adult and immature

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ticks belonging to 12 species (11 Ixodid and one Argasid) were collected. Eleven tick species were collected from Kallar area situated downhill eastern slopes of the Nilgiris followed by Burliar area (7 species) located at higher altitudes. From Masinagudi area near to dense forests and scrub jungles, five species were recorded. However, from Udhagamandalam area, at a higher elevation on the hills, only one species was recorded (Kumar *et al.*, 2014).

Ticks were sampled from domestic animals of Wayanad district of Kerala and *Rhipicephalus miropus* (52.71%) was identified to be the most prevalent species (Balasubramanian *et al.*, 2021). *Ixodes acutitarsus* and *I. ovatus* were reported mainly from eastern and north-eastern states of the country (Ghosh *et al.*, 2007). *Haemaphysalis bispinosa* and *R. (B.) microplus* are prevalent throughout India, while *H. spinigera* is restricted to southern states, central zones, Orissa and Mehalaya (Ghosh *et al.*, 2007). A total of 23 species of ticks were reported on domestic and wild animals from different parts of Kerala state

(Rajmohan, 1980; Ghosh *et al.*, 2007; Prakasan & Ramani, 2007).

The species of ixodid ticks reported from Kerala include *R. (B.) annulatus*, *R. (B.) microplus*, *R. (B.) decoloratus*, *R. sanguineus s.l.*, *R. haemaphysaloides*, *R. turanicus*, *H. bispinosa*, *H. intermedia*, *H. aculeata*, *H. cuspidata*, *H. knobigera*, *H. turturis*, *H. spinigera*, *H. anatolicum*, *H. isaaci*, *H. hussaini*, *A. intergrum*, *N. monstrosus* and *N. keralensis* (Rajamohan, 1980; Prakasan & Ramani, 2007; Ajith Kumar *et al.*, 2018).

Due to the aforesaid ticks, related epidemics occurred in different parts of India, thus, this group gains considerable importance. Even now there are reservoirs from which it might break into epidemics at any time. Thus, it is emphasized that there should be an establishment equipped with a permanent Tick surveillance system with improved facilities to assist in Tick-borne disease diagnostics and to initiate effective vector control efforts to stop the transmission of Tick-borne diseases in the future.

Figure 1. State wise distribution of ticks genera and species in India

Table 2. Host and distribution of all the valid updated tick species in India (Guglielmone *et al.*, 2015, 2023; Nijhof *et al.*, 2019)

S.No.	Species	Host	Distribution
1	<i>Argas abdussalami</i>	Fowl and vultures	GJ
2	<i>Argas gujaratensis</i>	Domestic and wild animals	GJ
3	<i>Argas hermanni</i>	Birds	JH, PB, MH
4	<i>Argas hoogstraali</i>	Domestic and wild animals	GJ
5	<i>Argas robertsi</i>	Vertebrates	TN, KA, WB
6	<i>Argas indicus</i>	Bats	RJ
7	<i>Argas persicus</i>	Poultry birds, Indian myna, pigeon, pheasant	AP, AR, BR, CG, DL, HR, HP, JK, MH, TN, UP, RJ, WB
8	<i>Argas soneshinei</i>	Bats	AN, DN
9	<i>Argas vespertilionis</i>	Bats	RJ, JK, PB
10	<i>Argas wilsoni</i>	Bats	RJ
11	<i>Ornithodoros chiropterphila</i>	Bats	KA, MH
12	<i>Ornithodoros coniceps</i>	Swallows	UP
13	<i>Ornithodoros faini</i>	Bats	MH & UP
14	<i>Ornithodoros indica</i>	Barking deer, <i>Muntijak</i>	HP
15	<i>Ornithodoros lahorensis</i>	Vertebrates	HP, JK
16	<i>Ornithodoros moubata</i>	Pigs	AP, AS, ML, MN, MZ, NL, SK, TR
17	<i>Ornithodoros piriformis</i>	Bats and rodents	HP & UP
18	<i>Ornithodoros savignyi</i>	Bats and rodents	GJ, AP, MP, MH, TN
19	<i>Ornithodoros tholozani</i>	Vertebrates (sheep, goat, and cattle)	JK, HP, PB
20	<i>Otobius megnini</i>	<i>Artiodactyla</i> , dog and man	MP, MH, TN
21	<i>Amblyomma clypeolatum</i>	Star tortoise (<i>Geochelone elegans</i>)	GJ, RJ, WB
22	<i>Amblyomma hebraeum</i>	Tiger	AS
23	<i>Amblyomma helvolum</i>	<i>Python reticulatus</i> , <i>Zamenis mucosus</i> , <i>Zamenis korros</i> , <i>Varanus salvator</i> , <i>Varanus nebulosus</i> , <i>Geoemyda grandis</i> , <i>Coluber onicephalus</i> , <i>Coelognathus radiatus</i> , <i>Triglyphedon dendrophylum</i> , <i>Iguana</i> , Vertebrate.	AN, OD, WB, HP
24	<i>Amblyomma integrum</i>	Buffalo, cattle, Sambar deer, <i>Felis viverrina</i> , wild pig, <i>Viverricula malaccensis</i> on bushes, under stone & vertebrates.	DL, GA, GJ, JK, KA, KL, HP, MH, OD, TN, WB
25	<i>Amblyomma javanense</i>	<i>Manis pentadactyla</i> , <i>Nicoria tricarinata</i> , <i>Manis crassi caudata</i> (Indian pangolin)	PB, BR, GJ, KA, MH, OD, UP, WB, TN
26	<i>Amblyomma kraneveldi</i>	<i>Python morulus</i>	KL
27	<i>Amblyomma leave</i>	<i>Python lurus</i>	AR, DL, GA, GJ, KA, MH, OD, PB, TN
28	<i>Amblyomma nitidum</i>	Sea snakes (<i>Laticauda colubrine</i> , <i>Laticauda laticaudatus</i> , <i>Laticauda semifasciatus</i>)	AN, PB

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S.No	Species	Host	Distribution
29	<i>Amblyomma pattoni</i>	Sambar, reptiles	KL, TN, UP & WB
30	<i>Amblyomma supinoi</i>	<i>Testudo elongate, Geomyda spinosa</i>	WB
31	<i>Amblyomma testudinarium</i>	<i>Muntiacus muntjak caginalls, Sus scrofa cristatus, Hylobates hoolock</i> and cattle, tree shrew, red jungle fowl, mithun, man, buffalo, bullock, goat deer, dog, tapir, horse, wild bear, wild pig, tiger, shrew.	AR, AS, KA, KL, MP, MH, ML, OD, PB, SK, WB, TN
32	<i>Amblyomma gervaisi</i>	<i>Naa tripudians, Varanus bengalensis, Naja naja, Ptyas mucosa</i>	AR, DL, CG, MH, MN, OD, TN, KL, KA, UP, WB
33	<i>Amblyomma varanense</i>	<i>Varanus salvator, Varanus nebulosus, tripudians, Python reticulatus, Zamensis mucosus, Bos frontalis, Ovis nahura, Bangarus fasciatus, Gongilophis conious, Naja bungarus, Naja tripudians, Python molourus, Vipera russelli</i>	AN, AS, BR, GA, MP, OD, UP, WB,
34	<i>Dermacentor atrosignatus</i>	Goat	UP
35	<i>Dermacentor auratus</i>	Barking deer, cattle, man, squirrel, goat, tree shrew, horse, <i>Rattus rattus brunneusculus</i> , bear, chital, civet cat, deer, <i>Felis pardus</i> , <i>Melursus ursinus</i> , Nias, pig, wild boar, wild pig	AN, AR, AS, BR, KA, KL, JK, MP, MH, ML, MN, MZ, PB, TR, OD, UP, WB
36	<i>Dermacentor raskemensis</i>	Vertebrates	JK, HP
37	<i>Haemaphysalis aborensis</i>	<i>Tupaia glis</i> , tiger, <i>Cervus unicolor</i> ssp., shrew, red jungle fowl and vegetation.	AP, AS, MN, ML, MZ, WB
38	<i>Haemaphysalis aculeata</i>	Deer, man, monkey, bird, cow, leopard, mongoose	KA, KL, TN
39	<i>Haemaphysalis anomala</i>	Cow, <i>Muntiacus muntjak vaginalis</i>	HP, AS, BR, ML, UP
40	<i>Haemaphysalis aponommoides</i>	Cattle, sambar, horse, vegetation.	AP, SK, WB
41	<i>Haemaphysalis birmaniae</i>	Sambar, <i>Antelope</i> , Indian muntjak, chital, domestic zhum, serow, goral, cow, man, <i>Muntiacus muntjak vaginalis, Cappricornis sumatraensis</i>	AR, AS, UP, MZ, WB
42	<i>Haemaphysalis bispinosa</i>	Barking deer, cattle, civet, cat, dog, sambar, tiger, Leopard, goat, pig, buffalo, spotted deer, donkey, pony, horse, sheep, dog, tiger, cat, monkey.	AP, AR, AN, AS, BR, GA, GJ, GJ, HP, KA, KL, JK, JH, MP, MH, MN, ML, MZ, OD, PB, SK, TN, TR, UP, WB
43	<i>Haemaphysalis campanulata</i>	Sambar, deer, wolf, cows, horse, dogs, rats, and man.	KL, BR, OD
44	<i>Haemaphysalis canestrinii</i>	Leopard, jackal, snake, <i>Rattus blanfordi, Rattus cutchicus</i>	AS, DL, BR, HP, MP, OD, PB, UP
45	<i>Haemaphysalis cheprai</i>	Wolf	BR, OD

S.No	Species	Host	Distribution
46	<i>Haemaphysalis cornigera</i>	Vertebrates	HP
47	<i>Haemaphysalis cornupunctata</i>	Vertebrates	JK, HP, UP
48	<i>Haemaphysalis cuspidata</i>	Rats, shrew, jackal, mouse deer, wild mammals, buffalo, cat, palm civet, birds species, mongoose, leopard.	KA,MH,KL, TN
49	<i>Haemaphysalis darjeeling</i>	<i>Muntiacus muntjak vaginalis</i> , <i>Capricornis sumatraensis</i> , <i>Sus scrofa cristatus</i>	AS,MN,WB
50	<i>Haemaphysalis davisi</i>	Cattle, goat, horse, mule, sheep, sambar, deer, hog hadger, tiger and vegetation.	AR,SK, MN
51	<i>Haemaphysalis doenitzi</i>	Domestic and wild animals	GJ, MH, KA, KL, PB
52	<i>Haemaphysalis fusca</i>	Dog	TN
53	<i>Haemaphysalis flava</i>	Vertebrates	TN
54	<i>Haemaphysalis formosensis</i>	Mammals	KA
55	<i>Haemaphysalis garhwalensis</i>	Vertebrates	HP, UK
56	<i>Haemaphysalis howletti</i>	Rodents, birds, crow pheasant, palm squirrel, Mongoose	HP, MH, UK, JK,UP
57	<i>Haemaphysalis hystricis</i>	Tree shrew, <i>Rattus rattus brunneusculus</i> , man and vegetation	AR, AS, UP, WB
58	<i>Haemaphysalis indica</i>	<i>Lepus sp.</i> , <i>Mus booduga</i> , ratel, palm civet cat, Leopard, <i>Tupaia glis</i> , Bengal fox, domestic dog, jackal, small and large mammals	BR, GJ, JK, KA, OD, KL, HP, MH, RJ, UP,WB AN, AP, AR, AS, CG, DL, GA, GJ, HP, HR, BR, KA,KL, JK, MH, MP, OD, TN, PB
59	<i>Haemaphysalis intermedia</i>	<i>Centropus sinensis</i> , cattle, goat, sheep, tiger, barking deer, vertebrates	BR, GJ, JK, KA, OD, KL, HP, MH, RJ, UP,WB AN, AP, AR, AS, CG, DL, GA, GJ, HP, HR, BR, KA,KL, JK, MH, MP, OD, TN, PB
60	<i>Haemaphysalis indoflava</i>	Vertebrates	TN, RJ, UK,UP
61	<i>Haemaphysalis japonica</i>	Cattle	KA, KL
62	<i>Haemaphysalis kashmirensis</i>	<i>Agama lizard</i> , rodents, Goat, sheep, cattle	HP, JK, SK, UP
63	<i>Haemaphysalis kinneari</i>	Tiger, monkey, rodent, buffalo, leopard, mongoose, wild dog, wild boar and Asiatic jackal.	KA, KL,TN, WB
64	<i>Haemaphysalis knobigera</i>	Cow and goat	KL
65	<i>Haemaphysalis kumaonensis</i>	Small and large mammals	BR, GJ, HP,JK, KA,MH,OD, RJ,UK
66	<i>Haemaphysalis kutchensis</i>	Hare and domestic animals	GJ,HP, MH, RJ, UP
67	<i>Haemaphysalis kysanurensis</i>	Tree shrew and <i>Gallus gallus</i>	AR, KA,KL, TN
68	<i>Haemaphysalis leachi</i>	<i>Canis aureus</i> & other vertebrates	TN, PB,KA, MH, GA, Ludhiana to Chandigarh road, PB
69	<i>Haemaphysalis longicornis</i>	Goat	
70	<i>Haemaphysalis megalaimae</i>	Birds' species and small green barbet from KFD area.	KA

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S.No.	Species	Host	Distribution
71	<i>Haemaphysalis minuta</i>	Forest undergrowth	GA, KA, KL, HP, MP, OD, UP
72	<i>Haemaphysalis montgomeryi</i>	Goat	HP, HR, JK, PB, UP, WB
73	<i>Haemaphysalis nepalensis</i>	Cattle, goat, sheep, yak	AR, MZ, SK
74	<i>Haemaphysalis obesa</i>	<i>Presbytis pileatus ssp.</i>	ML, WB
75	<i>Haemaphysalis ornithophila</i>	Birds and red jungle fowl and etc.	UK, UP
76	<i>Haemaphysalis papuana</i>	Bonnet monkey, langur, Indian wild boar, tiger and vegetation	AN, KA
77	<i>Haemaphysalis paraturturis</i>	Cattle, jungle, cow, bear, calf, bullock, wild dog, birds, mongoose, wild boar, wolf and carnivore.	AP, JH, BR, JK, MH, HP, MP, UK, UP, OD, MP, TN
78	<i>Haemaphysalis parva</i>	Wild animals	KA
79	<i>Haemaphysalis ramachandrai</i>	Cattle, goat, sheep, man, vegetation.	HP, SK, WB
80	<i>Haemaphysalis sambar</i>	Sambar deer	KL
81	<i>Haemaphysalis shimoga</i>	Sambar deer, goat, cattle, sheep and cow.	KA, KL, ML, HP, AS, WB, AR, SK, TN
82	<i>Haemaphysalis silvafelis</i>	Vertebrates	AP, MH, OD
83	<i>Haemaphysalis spinigera</i>	Panther, near, tiger, leopard, buffalo, sheep, cow, man, langur gaur, bison, cat, fowl, small Indian civet, deer, dog, rodent, shrew, mongoose, crow, Malabar giant, peacock, bulbul and other vertebrates.	AN, AP, AR, HP, AS, CG, GA, GJ, MP, MH, ML, KA, KL, OD, TN, WB
84	<i>Haemaphysalis sulcata</i>	Goat and sheep	PB, HP, AR, JK
85	<i>Haemaphysalis sundrai</i>	Cattle, sheep, barking deer.	PB, WB, HP, UK, UP
86	<i>Haemaphysalis turturis</i>	Cow, goat, Indian wild boar	AN, AP, GA, GJ, WB, KA, KL, MH, OD, TN, UP
87	<i>Haemaphysalis warburtoni</i>	Sheep, goat, yak, cattle, man, rodent and vertebrates.	UP
88	<i>Haemaphysalis wellingtoni</i>	Birds, goose, domestic fowl, wild fowl, dog, bonnet monkey, turkey, langur.	AN, AS, KA, MH, OD, KL, TN, WB
89	<i>Hyalomma aegyptium</i>	Vertebrates	TN
90	<i>Hyalomma anatolicum</i>	Cattle, horse, camel, goat, donkey, bear and cow	Throughout India
91	<i>Hyalomma brevipunctata</i>	Cattle	AP, BR, DL, JH, OD, PB, TN, UP, WB
92	<i>Hyalomma dromedarii</i>	Cattle and camel	AP, DL, GJ, OD, HP, HR, MH, JK, PB, RJ
93	<i>Hyalomma excavatum</i>	Vertebrates	TN
94	<i>Hyalomma hussaini</i>	Cattle, buffalo, sheep, goat, domestic animals	AP, BR, CG, DL, GA, GJ, HP, HR, JK, JH, KA, MP, MH, OD, PB, RJ, SK, TN, UP, WB

S.No.	Species	Host	Distribution
95	<i>Hyalomma isaaci</i>	Buffalo, cow, horse, sheep, myna, rabbit, birds, cattle, goat, dog, hare, camel and man	AP, AR, BR, CG, DL, GJ, HP, HR, JK, JH, KA, MP, MH, OD, PB, RJ, TN, UP, WB
96	<i>Hyalomma kumari</i>	Dog, cattle, goat, horse, buffalo, sheep, camel, tiger, barking deer and Indian Muntjac	AS, BR, DL, GJ, KL, JH, OD, PB, MP, MH, TN, UP, HP, HR, RJ, KL, KA, GJ, JK, MH, RJ, UP
97	<i>Hyalomma marginatum</i>	Domestic and wild animals	UP
98	<i>Hyalomma turanicum</i>	Cattle	GJ, MH, UP,
99	<i>Ixodes acutitarsus</i>	Cattle and vegetation	AR, AS, HP, SK, UP, WB
100	<i>Ixodes ceylonensis</i>	Small mammals and including shrew (<i>Suncus murinus</i>)	KA, KL, TN
101	<i>Ixodes cookei</i>	Cattle	AR
102	<i>Ixodes granulatus</i>	<i>Epimys rufescens</i> , <i>Sciurus erythraeus intermedius</i> .	AR, AS, HP, UP, WB, NL, SK
103	<i>Ixodes himalayensis</i>	Vertebrates	HP, JK
104	<i>Ixodes holocyclus</i>	Red squirrel and <i>Sciurus variabilis</i>	Eastern India (WB)
105	<i>Ixodes kashmiricus</i>	Cattle, flying squirrel, <i>Tupaia glis</i>	AR, HP, JK, UP
106	<i>Ixodes ovatus</i>	Dog, cattle, goat, sheep, small mammals, yak, vegetation, tree shrew, mule, yak, man	AR, HP, JK, MN, MZ, SK, UP, WB
107	<i>Ixodes persulcatus</i>	Pets, livestock	HP, GR, KL, KA, AP, ML, MN, NL, AS, DL
108	<i>Ixodes radfordi</i>	Rodents including <i>Rattus r. rufescens</i>	MN
109	<i>Ixodes ricinus</i>	Dog	JK
110	<i>Ixodes turdus</i>	Vegetation	UP
111	<i>Ixodes vespertilionis</i>	<i>Taaphozous kacchensis</i> , <i>Rhinolophus affinis</i> .	AR, KA, RJ
112	<i>Nosomma keralensis</i>	Buffalo	KL
113	<i>Nosomma monstrosom</i>	Buffalo, cattle, sambar deer <i>Mus buduga</i> , domestic and wild animals	BR, DL, GA, GJ, JK, HP, MH, MP, OD, KA, KL, TN, PJ, UP, SK, WB
114	<i>Rhipicephalus annulatus</i>	Vertebrates, Sambar deer, Spotter deer, Barking deer, Mouse deer, Wild big	GJ, JK, TN, KA, KL
115	<i>Rhipicephalus australis</i>	Cattle	WB, AN, AS
116	<i>Rhipicephalus bursa</i>	Vertebrates	TN
117	<i>Rhipicephalus decoloratus</i>	Cow	JK
118	<i>Rhipicephalus haemaphysaloides</i>	<i>Muntiacus muntjak vaginalis</i> , buffalo, cattle, goat, leopard, sheep, dog, man, jackal, rodents and shrews.	Throughout India
119	<i>Rhipicephalus indicus</i>	Vertebrates	TN
120	<i>Rhipicephalus microplus</i>	Vertebrates	Throughout India
121	<i>Rhipicephalus ramachandrai</i>	Small and large animals	RJ, GJ, KA, MH, PB, RJ, UP

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122	<i>Rhipicephalus sanguineus</i>	Dog, cattle, jackal and bullock, wild big,	Throughout India
123	<i>Rhipicephalus scalpturatus</i>	Vertebrates	ML
124	<i>Rhipicephalus simus</i>	Vertebrates	TN
125	<i>Rhipicephalus turanicus</i>	Cattle, dogs, rodents and shrews.	AP, CG, GJ, HP, JK, MP, MH, TN, WB, PB

AN-Andaman and Nicobar; AP- Andhra Pradesh; AR-Arunachal Pradesh; AS-Assam; BR-Bihar; CG-Chandigarh; DN-Dadra and Nagar Haveli; DL-Delhi; GA-Goa; GJ-Gujarat; HR-Haryana; HP-Himachal Pradesh; JK-Jammu and Kashmir; JH-Jharkhand; KA-Karnataka; KL-Kerala; MP-Madhya Pradesh; MH-Maharashtra; MN-Manipur; ML-Meghalaya; MZ-Mizoram; NL-Nagaland; OD-Odisha; PB-Punjab; RJ-Rajasthan; SK-Sikkim; TN-Tamil Nadu; TR-Tripura; UP-Uttar Pradesh; UK-Uttarakhand; WB-West Bengal.

Table 3. List of tick species recorded in India

S.No	Species	References
1	<i>Argas abdussalami</i> Hoogstraal & McCarthy, 1965	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
2	<i>Argas gujaratensi</i> Advani & Vazirani 1981	ibid
3	<i>Argas hermanni</i> Audouin, 1826	ibid
4	<i>Argas hoogstraali</i> Morel & Vassiliades, 1965	ibid
5	<i>Argas robertsi</i> Hoogstraal Kaiser & Kohls, 1968 ^A	ibid
6	<i>Argas indicus</i> Advani & Vazirani 1981	ibid
7	<i>Argas reflexus</i> Hoogstraal & Kohls, 1960	(Miranpuri <i>et al.</i> , 1975; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
8	<i>Argas persicus</i> (Oken, 1818)	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; 2023)
9	<i>Argas soneshinei</i> Advani & Vazirani 1981	ibid
10	<i>Argas vespertilionis</i> (Latreille, 1796)	ibid
11	<i>Argas wilsoni</i> Advani & Vazirani 1981	ibid
12	<i>Ornithodoros chiropterphila</i> Dhanda & Rajagopalan, 1971	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
13	<i>Ornithodoros coniceps</i> (Canestrini, 1890)	ibid
14	<i>Ornithodoros crossi</i> Brumpt 1922 ^{A1}	ibid
15	<i>Ornithodoros faini</i> Hoogstraal, 1960	ibid
16	<i>Ornithodoros indica</i> Rau & Rao, 1971	(Rau & Rao, 1971)
17	<i>Ornithodoros lahorensis</i> Neumann, 1908	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
18	<i>Ornithodoros moubata</i> Murray, 1877	(Negi <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
19	<i>Ornithodoros piriformis</i> Warburton, 1918	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
20	<i>Ornithodoros savignyi</i> (Audouin, 1827)	ibid
21	<i>Ornithodoros tholozani</i> (Laboulbene & Megnin, 1882)	(Sanyal & De, 2005; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
22	<i>Otobius megnini</i> (Duges, 1883)	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Soundararajan <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
23	<i>Amblyomma clypeolatum</i> Neumann, 1899	ibid
24	<i>Amblyomma hebraeum</i> Koch, 1844	ibid
25	<i>Amblyomma helvolum</i> Koch, 1844	ibid
26	<i>Amblyomma integrum</i> Karsch, 1879	(Tiwari & Hiriyani, 1988, 1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Ajith Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Balasubramanian <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
27	<i>Amblyomma javanense</i> (Supino, 1897)	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Ajith Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
28	<i>Amblyomma kraneveldi</i> Anastos, 1956	(Ajith Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2018)

S.No.	Species	References
29	<i>Amblyomma leave</i> Koch, 1844	(Sanyal & De, 2001; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
30	<i>Amblyomma mudaliari</i> Rao, hiregaudar & Alwar, 1964 ^B	(Sanyal, 2011)
31	<i>Amblyomma nitidum</i> Hirst & Hirst, 1910	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
32	<i>Amblyomma subleave</i> ^C	(Sharif, 1928; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
33	<i>Amblyomma supinoi</i> Neumann, 1905	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
34	<i>Amblyomma testudinarium</i> Koch, 1844	(Tiwari & Hiriyani, 1988, 1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
35	<i>Amblyomma varanense</i> (Supino, 1897)	(Sanyal & De, 2001; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
36	<i>Aponomma gervaisi</i> (Lucas 1847) ^D	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Ajith Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
37	<i>Aponomma pattoni</i> Neumann 1910 ^E	ibid
38	<i>Aponomma lucasi</i> Warburton ^F	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997)
39	<i>Dermacentor atrosignatus</i> Neumann, 1906	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
40	<i>Dermacentor auratus</i> Supino, 1897	(Tiwari & Hiriyani, 1988, 1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
41	<i>Dermacentor raskemensis</i> Pomerantzev, 1946	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
42	<i>Haemaphysalis aborensis</i> Warburton, 1913	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
43	<i>Haemaphysalis aculeata</i> Larvarra, 1904	(Tiwari & Hiriyani, 1988, 1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Naren Babu <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
44	<i>Haemaphysalis anomala</i> Warburton, 1913	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
45	<i>Haemaphysalis aponommoides</i> Warburton, 1913	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
46	<i>Haemaphysalis birmaniae</i> Supine, 1897	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> 1997; Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
47	<i>Haemaphysalis bispinosa</i> Neumann, 1897	(Tiwari & Hiriyani, 1988, 1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Ajith Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Balasubramanian <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
48	<i>Haemaphysalis campanulata</i> Warburton, 1908	ibid
49	<i>Haemaphysalis canestrinii</i> (Supino, 1897)	ibid
50	<i>Haemaphysalis centropi</i> Kohls, 1949 ^{F1}	(Miranpuri <i>et al.</i> , 1975)
51	<i>Haemaphysalis choprai</i> Shariff, 1928 ^G	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
52	<i>Haemaphysalis cholodkovskyi</i> Olenev, 1928 ^H	ibid
53	<i>Haemaphysalis cornigera</i> Neumann, 1897	(Sanyal & De, 2005)
54	<i>Haemaphysalis cornupunctata</i> Hoogstraal & Varma, 1962	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
55	<i>Haemaphysalis cuspidata</i> Warburton, 1910	(Tiwari & Hiriyani, 1988, 1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Naren Babu <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Balasubramanian <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
56	<i>Haemaphysalis darjeeling</i> Hoogstraal & Dhanda, 1970	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
57	<i>Haemaphysalis davisii</i> Hoogstraal, Dhanda & Bhat, 1970	ibid
58	<i>Haemaphysalis doenitzi</i> Warburton & Nuttall, 1909	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Naren Babu <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)

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S.No.	Species	References
59	<i>Haemaphysalis fusca</i> Christophers, 1907	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
60	<i>Haemaphysalis flava</i> Neumann, 1897	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011)
61	<i>Haemaphysalis formosensis</i> Neumann, 1913	(Mehla <i>et al.</i> , 2009)
62	<i>Haemaphysalis garhwalensis</i> Dhanda & Bhat,1968	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
63	<i>Haemaphysalis himalaya</i> Hoogstraal, 1966 ¹	ibid
64	<i>Haemaphysalis howletti</i> Warburton, 1913	ibid
65	<i>Haemaphysalis hystricis supine</i> , 1897	ibid
66	<i>Haemaphysalis indica</i> Warburton, 1910	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Ajith Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
67	<i>Haemaphysalis intermedia</i> Warburton & Nuttall, 1909	(Tiwari & Hiriyan, 1988,1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Negi <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
68	<i>Haemaphysalis indoflava</i> Dhanda & Bhat, 1968	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
69	<i>Haemaphysalis japonica</i> Warburton, 1913	(Krishnamoorthy <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
70	<i>Haemaphysalis kashmirensis</i> Hoogstraal & Varma, 1962	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
71	<i>Haemaphysalis kinneari</i> Warbuton, 1913	(Tiwari & Hiriyan, 1988, 1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Naren Babu <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
72	<i>Haemaphysalis knobigera</i> Prakasan & Ramani, 2007	(Prakasan & Ramani, 2007)
73	<i>Haemaphysalis kumaonensis</i> Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011	(Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011)
74	<i>Haemaphysalis kutchensis</i> Hoogstrall & Trapido, 1963	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
75	<i>Haemaphysalis kysanurensis</i> Trapido, Hoogstraal & Rajagopalan, 1964	(Tiwari & Hiriyan, 1988,1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997,Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Naren Babu <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Balasubramanian <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
76	<i>Haemaphysalis leachi</i> (Audouin,1826)	(Sanyal, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Naren Babu <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
77	<i>Haemaphysalis megalaimae</i> Rajagopalan, 1963	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Naren Babu <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
78	<i>Haemaphysalis minuta</i> Kohls, 1950	(Tiwari & Hiriyan, 1988,1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Naren Babu <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
79	<i>Haemaphysalis montgomeryi</i> Nuttall, 1912	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
80	<i>Haemaphysalis nepalensis</i> Hoogstraal, 1962	ibid
81	<i>Haemaphysalis neumanni</i> Donitz,1905 ¹¹	(Miranpuri <i>et al.</i> , 1975; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
82	<i>Haemaphysalis obesa</i> Larrousse, 1925	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
83	<i>Haemaphysalis ornithophila</i> Hoogstraal & Khols, 1959	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)

S.No.	Species	References
84	<i>Haemaphysalis papuana</i> Thorell, 1883	(De & Sanyal, 1984)
85	<i>Haemaphysalis paraturturis</i> Hoogstraal, Trapido & Rebelello, 1963	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
86	<i>Haemaphysalis parva</i> (Neumann, 1897)	(Shariff, 1928)
87	<i>Haemaphysalis ramachandrai</i> Dhanda, Hoogstraal & Bhar, 1970	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
88	<i>Haemaphysalis sambar</i> Hoogstraal, 1971	ibid
89	<i>Haemaphysalis shimoga</i> Trapido & Hoogstraal, 1964	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Ajith Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Naren Babu <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
90	<i>Haemaphysalis silvafelis</i> Hoogstraal & Trapido,1963	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2014)
91	<i>Haemaphysalis spinigera</i> Neumann, 1897	(Tiwari & Hiriyan, 1988,1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Ajith Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Balasubramanian <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Negi <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
92	<i>Haemaphysalis sulcata</i> Canestrini & Fanzago, 1878	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
93	<i>Haemaphysalis sundrai</i> Sharif, 1928	ibid
94	<i>Haemaphysalis turturis</i> Nuttall & Warburton, 1915	(Tiwari & Hiriyan, 1988,1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Naren Babu <i>et al.</i> , 2019; Balasubramanian <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Negi <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
95	<i>Haemaphysalis warburtoni</i> Nuttall,1912	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
96	<i>Haemaphysalis wellingtoni</i> Nuttall & Warburton, 1908	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Naren Babu <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
97	<i>Hyalomma aegyptium</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	(Sanyal, 2011)
98	<i>Hyalomma anatolicum</i> Koch, 1844	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
99	<i>Hyalomma brevipunctata</i> Sharif,1928	ibid
100	<i>Hyalomma datritum</i> Schulze,1919	ibid
101	<i>Hyalomma dromedarii</i> Koch, 1844	ibid
102	<i>Hyalomma excavatum</i> Koch, 1844	(Sanyal, 2011)
103	<i>Hyalomma hussaini</i> Sharif, 1928	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
104	<i>Hyalomma hystricis</i> Dhanda & Raja, 1974	ibid
105	<i>Hyalomma isaaci</i> Sharif, 1928	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Soundararajan <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
106	<i>Hyalomma kumari</i> Sharif, 1928	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
107	<i>Hyalomma marginatum</i> Koch, 1844	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Balasubramanian <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Negi <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
108	<i>Hyalomma turanicum</i> Pomerantzev, 1946	(Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
109	<i>Ixodes acutitarsus</i> (Karsch,1880)	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)

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S.No.	Species	References
110	<i>Ixodes ceylonensis</i> Kohls,1950	(Tiwari & Hiriyan, 1988,1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
111	<i>Ixodes cookei</i> Packard, 1869	(Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
112	<i>Ixodes granulatus</i> Supino, 1897	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997,Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
113	<i>Ixodes himalayensis</i> Dhanda & Kulkarni,1969	ibid
114	<i>Ixodes holocyclus</i> Neuman, 1899	ibid
115	<i>Ixodes kasmiricus</i> Pomerantzev,1948	ibid
116	<i>Ixodes kempfi</i> Nuttall, 1914 ^J	(Sanyal & De, 2006)
117	<i>Ixodes ovatus</i> Neumann, 1899	(Tiwari & Hiriyan, 1988,1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
118	<i>Ixodes petauristae</i> Warburton, 1933	ibid
119	<i>Ixodes radfordi</i> Kohls, 1948	(Tiwari & Hiriyan, 1988,1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011;
120	<i>Ixodes ricinus</i> (Linnaeus,1758)	(Sharif, 1928)
121	<i>Ixodes turdus</i> Nakatsuji,1942	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
122	<i>Ixodes vespertilionis</i> Koch, 1844	ibid
123	<i>Nosomma keralensis</i> Prakasan & Ramani, 2007	(Prakasan & Ramani, 2007)
124	<i>Nosomma monstrosum</i> (Nuttall & Warburton, 1908)	(Tiwari & Hiriyan, 1988,1989; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011;
125	<i>Rhipicephalus arakeri</i> Hiregauder, 1975 ^K	(Sanyal & De, 2004)
126	<i>Rhipicephalus annulatus</i> (Say, 1821)	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> 1997; Ajith Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
127	<i>Rhipicephalu annulatus</i> subsp. <i>calcaratus</i> Sharif,1928 ^L	(Sharif, 1928; Tiwari & Hiriyan, 1988,1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997;Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
128	<i>Rhipicephalus australis</i> Fuller,1899	(Sharif, 1928)
129	<i>Rhipicephalus bursa</i> Canestrini & Fanzago, 1878	(Sanyal, 2011)
130	<i>Rhipicephalus decoloratus</i> Koch, 1844	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997)
131	<i>Rhipicephalus haemaphysaloides</i> Supino,1897	(Tiwari & Hiriyan, 1988,1989; Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Geevarghese & Mishra, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Ajith Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Soundararajan <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
132	<i>Rhipicephalus indus</i> Mining,1936 ^M	(Sanyal, 2011)
133	<i>Rhipicephalus microplus</i> (Canestrini, 1888)	(Sanyal, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
134	<i>Rhipicephalus ramachandrai</i> Dhanda, 1966	ibid
135	<i>Rhipicephalus sanguineus</i> (Latreille, 1806)	(Sanyal, 2011; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Ajith Kumar <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Balasubramanian <i>et al.</i> , 2021)
136	<i>Rhipicephalus scalpturatus</i> Santos Dias, 1959	ibid
137	<i>Rhipicephalus simus</i> Koch, 1844	(Sanyal, 2011)
138	<i>Rhipicephalus turanicus</i> Pomerantzev, 1940	(Geevarghese <i>et al.</i> , 1997; Ghosh <i>et al.</i> , 2015)

^Asynonym for *Argas hermanni* (3); ^{A1}synonym for *Ornithodoros tholozani*(20); ^Bsynonym for *Amblyomma integrum*(25); ^Csynonym for *Amblyomma javanense* (26); ^Dsynonym for *Amblyomma gervaisi* (33); ^Esynonym for *Amblyomma pattoni* (33); ^Fsynonym for *Amblyomma varanensis*(34); ^{F1} synonym for *Haemaphysalis*

doenitzi (56); ^Gsynonym for *Haemaphysalis choprai* (48); ^Hsynonym for *Haemaphysalis sulcata* (86); ^Isynonym for *Haemaphysalis sundrai* (87); ^{II} synonym for *Haemaphysalis longicornis*.; ^Jsynonym for *Ixodes granulatus* (106); ^Ksynonym for *Rhipicephalus ramachandrai* (128); ^Lsynonym for *Rhipicephalus annulatus* (120); ^Msynonym for *Rhipicephalus microplus* (127) (Guglielmone *et al.*, 2015; Nijhof *et al.*, 2019)

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